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CHANGES IN LABORATORY TESTS IN PATIENTS WITH CORONAVIRUS DISEASE

Introduction.

The presence of coronavirus infection was verified by clinical manifestation, results of PCR, instrumental methods of examination, and other laboratory tests included in the protocol of diagnostics and treatment tactics accepted at the state level. Blood was taken from the finger of the sick and practically healthy people on an empty stomach (7-8 a.m) and carried out clinical and general blood analysis. Based on the results of the clinical blood analysis, we calculated immunohistological coefficients and indices, which determined the level of adaptive tension of the body and the type of individual tension of each patient.

To establish the immunoenzyme changes of the mentioned indicators as possible prognostic factors we determined: the degree of disturbance of the level of adaptive tension and cellular reactivity of the organism of patients with coronavirus disease according to the formula: Degree of impairment of immuno- hematological index = (index of the patient/index of the controlled practically healthy person) - 1 × 100%. In the case of deficit, the indices were negative (-), the sign (+) indicates hyperfunctioning of the system. The result value within the range 1-33% is interpreted as the first (I) level of disorders, 34-67% - the second (II) level, over 67% - the third (III) level of disorders.

The aim. Coronavirus disease is one of the dramatic problems of modern medicine. Nature presented mankind with a threatening message that the evolution of life on Earth is not over and ecological disturbances have disastrous consequences. Scientists of the world are faced with a task that, if successfully resolved, will in some way depend on the continued survival of humanity. A new disease that is spreading rapidly is characterized by several peculiarities. This rapid fluidity of the virus, high prevalence rate, specific pathogenesis, and clinical manifestation, etc.

Materials and methods. Analysis of literature sources on this topic.

Key words: Coronavirus disease, adaptive process, cell reactivity, pneumonia, bilateral lung damage

Results. Despite the obvious severity of the situation, the combined efforts of scientists in the fight against the pandemic of coronavirus infection will already lead to a significant success: Detailed characterization of the causative agent, determining the mechanism of infection spread, grounded and put into practice methods of laboratory diagnostics, created a base of production doses of commercial test systems, most importantly, over a remarkably short period created, tested vaccines, which made it possible to substantiate promising approaches to therapeutic tactics and prophylaxis. At the same time, variability of clinical manifestation requires the study of pathogenetic mechanisms of disease manifestation, especially at the initial stages. It is important to establish the adaptation-compensatory mechanisms and related cellular reactivity of the organism of patients, which not only need to be used to solve diagnostic problems, treatment, and determination of the prognosis of the disease course.

Discussion. Coronavirus disease is a severe respiratory viral infection with airborne transmission caused by a new coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2), which affects people of different ages and occurs in the form of

asymptomatic, mild, and severe forms with the development of atypical pneumonia, severe acute respiratory syndrome, which can lead to death. Based on the examination of absolute and relative numbers of the main populations of immunocompetent cells of peripheral blood to determine the level of adaptation pressure and cell reactivity of the organism of the patients with coronavirus disease on admission to hospital treatment.

It is important to establish the adaptation and positional mechanisms and associated cellular reactivity of the body of patients, which not only need to be used to solve diagnostic problems, treatment, and determination of the prognosis of the disease course. Coronavirus disease is associated with an 86.96% increase in the level of adaptive tension in the relative number of immunocompetent cells and a 56.86% increase in the absolute number of immunocompetent cells.

Clinical and laboratory tests were performed on 20 patients with coronavirus disease in the infectious disease department of Regional Clinical Hospital "Chernivtsi", all patients agreed to participate in clinical and laboratory tests.

The results of clinical and laboratory examinations of 30 practically healthy persons of the same age (average age 63.17 ± 3.17 years, the average age of those who had coronavirus disease was 64.57 ± 4.27 years) were used for the study comparison.

The majority of patients had a moderate course of the disease, and only 7% of patients had a severe course of the disease. Every patient admitted to the hospital was diagnosed with bronchial and lung lesions, which were confirmed by X-ray and computer tomography (CT). In the structure of diagnosed pneumonia, bilateral lung damage prevailed (98.3%). Symptoms of gastrointestinal tract involvement were observed in 11 patients (16.9%).

The diagnosis was confirmed by nasopharyngeal smears, which were taken by dacron swabs with subsequent placement in a transport medium for respiratory smears. Biological material was collected in the first 24 hours from the moment of hospitalization of patients with signs of ARVI and suspicion of COVID-19 and examined by PCR method. All patients obtained positive results.

The number of neutrophilic granulocytes was shown to increase by 9.75% with a significant increase in the absolute and relative number of band cells by 5.05 times in patients with coronavirus disease (CVC) and myelocytes were found in 35% of the patients. At the same time, the total number of eosinophilic granulocytes decreased by 55.94% while maintaining their absolute number. The total number of granulocytes in peripheral blood of patients decreased by 14.23%, which form a specific immune response and antigen. There is a significant decrease of relative (2.25 times) and absolute (330 times) monocytes, macrophages, which perform at least the protective, antigen-presenting and secretory functions.

Today there are suggested simple criteria for the evaluation of general adaptive reactions that develop in the body due to the influence of external and internal subunits. These methods can be used to assess the nature of non-specific action of various agents, pathogens, and others, as well as to determine the efficacy of targeted activation therapeutic practice and to predict the course of the disease. The adaptation of the human body to any extreme conditions - stresses, illness, injuries, operational stresses is ensured by its reserves.

Based on the ideas of G. Selye about the reaction of nonspecific adaptive stress syndrome, the existence of the occurring nonspecific adaptive reactions of the organism in succession is presented and it is established that the action of each of them is the level of the value of the adaptive coefficient of performance.

The prognostic value of the adaptation coefficient is determined, and the prevalence of some other non-specific adaptation reactions of the organism is detected. The following adaptive reactions of the organism were determined: stress, training, calm activation reaction, increased activation, and overactivation. Adaptation index is used as an integrated test, calculated by the ratio of the absolute and relative number of lymphocytes and segmented neutrophils. Adaptive reactions of the human organism is closely connected with the cellular reactivity of the organism, the level of

which is determined by the indices of the absolute and relative number of the main populations of immunocompetent cells in the peripheral blood.

Conclusion. The prognostic value of the adaptation coefficient is determined, and the prevalence of some other non-specific adaptation reactions of the organism is detected. The following adaptive reactions of the organism were determined: stress, training, calm activation reaction, increased activation, and overactivation. Adaptation index is used as an integrated test, calculated by the ratio of the absolute and relative number of lymphocytes and segmented neutrophils.

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